

UMERC+METS 2024 Conference

7-9 August | Duluth, MN, USA

Modeling the Electrical output from a CEC using Machine Learning Emily Alvarado^{a,b,*}, Jeremy Kasper^a, Phylcia Cicilio^{a,c}

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Abstract

Remote communities in Alaska have some of the highest costs of electricity in the United States. Due to the remote nature of these communities, transporting current energy converters (CECs) and the necessary infrastructure is logistically challenging and costly. The Tanana River Test Site (TRTS) was established about an hour's drive away from the University of Alaska Fairbanks as a location with many of the challenges of remote Alaska without being as remote. In efforts to streamline the process of implementing CECs in remote locations, we created a blackbox model to simulate the performance of a vertical axis CEC deployed at the TRTS. This model, generated with machine learning, accounts for the resource velocity and electrical load and outputs the current and voltage produced by the CEC. This presentation will show the validation of our model with field data from the vertical axis CEC at the TRTS and discuss the next steps to apply this research to other remote locations.

Keywords: Curent Energy Converters; Machine Learning; Power Eletronics
